

Analysis of the Effect of Halal Products, Packaging, Motivation, Price and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions, and its Implications on Repurchase of Multivitamin Redoxon in the New Normal Era After the Covid - 19 Pandemic in DKI Jakarta

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the influence of halal products, packaging, motivation, price and brand image on the consumer's purchase decision and the implications for repurchasing multivitamin R edoxon. In this study there are five independent variables namely Halal Products, Packaging, Motivation, Price and Brand Image and the dependent variables are purchase decision dan and repurchase. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to the research sample. The samples in this study were 120 people who were consumers of redoxon multivitamins located in DKI Jakarta. Based on the analysis and testing of the hypothesis, it was found that the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta was significantly influenced by product halalness, packaging, and motivation, while the effect on price and brand image was not significant. Furthermore, consumption decisions have a significant positive effect on Redoxon multivitamin repurchasing in DKI Jakarta.

Keywords:- Halal Products, Packaging, Motivation, Price, Repurchase, and Purchase Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

The public's need for multivitamins, especially those containing high doses of vitamin C, during the Covid-19 pandemic has increased. The increasing public needs for multivitamins is an opportunity for multivitamin producers, but on the other hand the competition between producers is also increasing. The Redoxon vitamin brand experienced the highest sales growth during the covid-19 pandemic (2020 to 2021). However, based on the total market share of vitamins, Redoxon is ranked third. The public's decision to choose and consume a certain brand of multivitamin is determined by several factors.

Based on preliminary research, consumers make purchases and consume Redoxon Multivitamin reinforced by two factors, namely external and internal actors. In term of internal factors, most consumers consume and buy multivitamin Redoxon because of the need for multivitamins

to maintain the imunity and health. For the external factor, the reason of consumers consuming redoxon multivitamins is the packaging attractive, Brand Image factor, halal product, and price.

The majority of Indonesia's population is Muslim, therefore the product halalness must be a serious concern for product manufacturers. The Halal label is very important for most Indonesian people to convince consumers that the product they purchase is a Halal product so that it becomes an important factor and consideration for consumers in deciding to buy or not buy a product (Syahputra & Hamoraon, 2013). From this opinion there is a tendency that consumers will not buy the product if there is no halal label because they feel doubtful about the halalness of the product.

Packaging has a very important role in attracting consumers to buy a product because basically packaging is the first object that consumers see when buying a product. The existence of attractive packaging trends can encourage consumers to choose a product even though consumers are not familiar with the product. According to Raheem (2014) packaging is a factor that plays a significant role in influencing consumers in making purchase decisions. Aspects of packaging that can influence purchasing decisions include color, packaging materials and packaging design. The increasing demand for multivitamins is driven by the community's motivation to maintain stamina and imunity to maintain health so as to minimize exposure to the Covid-19 virus. According to Sigit (in Satriaso, 2011), purchase motivation is an encouragement both rationally and emotionally felt by consumers to buy a product.

Consumer considerations in choosing a product to buy are inseparable from the price factor. In general, consumers will check or find out the price of a product when they are interested in buying the product so that consumers will consider the fairness and suitability of the price with the benefits of the product and to measure their ability to buy the product. According to Dharmmestha (in Grace, 2014) in general, products that have lower prices than other products have a higher tendency to be chosen by consumers. In

consumer's point of view, the price of Redoxon's vitamin C is considered affordable, so that its sales are quite high compared to other vitamins.

Redoxon vitamins are well known in public because they contain high doses of Vitamin C so that they are more efficacious in increasing stamina and immunity. Based on the Top Brand Award, Redoxon occupies the fourth position of the brand which is the Top of Domain Product Category Vitamin C. According to Foster (2016) brand image becomes a factor that influences purchase decisions significantly. It is considered that the better brand image of a product, the higher the tendency of consumers to decide to buy the product. In general, consumers tend to choose to buy products that are well known and have a good image compared to products whose brands are unknown or even have a bad image. In general, after consumers buy a product and feel the benefits of the product, consumers will evaluate how much the product can satisfy their wants and needs. Consumers who are satisfied with the benefits of the products they have purchased and consumed have a high tendency to repurchase these products, and vice versa (Kotler & Keller, 2021).

II. THEORY REVIEW

➤ *Repurchase Intention*

Repurchase is consumer behavior as a response that is created from satisfaction after buying a product or service. Repurchase intention reflects the desire of consumers to rebuy a product in the future. Repurchase behavior can also be interpreted as purchases made by consumers of the same brand repeatedly (Tjiptono in Fauzi, 2021). Repurchase can also reflect the many consumer experiences consuming products from the same brand and have a good evaluation of the product brand. Repurchase intention consists of four dimensions, namely transactional intention, referential intention, and preferential intention. Transactional intention is characterized by a consumer intention in repurchasing a product from the same brand. Preferential intention is characterized by the willingness of consumers to tell good things about a product from a certain brand and recommend it to others. Preferential intention is characterized by consumer behavior that chooses a product from a certain brand as the main choice compared to products from other brands. Explorative intention is characterized by the desire of consumers to seek deeper information about products from certain brands.

➤ *Purchase Decision*

Basically, purchase decision is consumer actions in making decisions to buy or not to buy a product (Schiffman and Kanuk in Oscar and Keni, 2019). Decisions made by consumers in making purchases occur after consumers carry out the process of evaluating a product, comparing it with many other alternative products, then adjusting it to their interests and needs and finally choosing the product that best suits their interests and which is considered the most beneficial or profitable. Systematically, purchasing decisions occur through five stages, including the problem recognition stage, which is the stage where consumers identify problems and their needs for a product, the information search stage,

where consumers looking for information on the product needed, the alternative evaluation stage, the stage where consumers compare a product with other products. and consider which products can provide more benefits and advantages, the purchasing decision stage, namely the stage where the consumer finally decides to buy a product, and the post-purchase behavior stage, namely the stage where the consumer evaluates their experience in consuming a product and assesses how much the product can satisfy them so that it can determine future behavior.

➤ *Halal Product*

Halal products are basically products that are permissible and do not contradict with Islamic religious law either from a material aspect (does not contain pork, alcohol, blood), methods of slaughtering, and processing methods that may not be mixed in the slightest with materials or materials that are not halal (Burhan in Mutiara and Syahputra, 2018). For consumers who are Muslim, information about product halalness is very important and greatly influences purchasing behavior (Saputra and Tresnati in Fadilah et al, 2020). In general, consumers will identify the halalness of a product from the halal label on the packaging of a product, therefore the halal label greatly influences purchase intention (Refmasita, Amar and Larasati, 2020) and purchase decisions (Febriyana, Sampurno, and Djoharsyah, 2019).

➤ *Packaging*

Packaging is basically all activities related to the design and production of containers used for a product. Packaging can be defined from its function, namely as a material used to wrap products that functions to protect the product, keep the product's hygiene, accommodate the product, identify the product, explain the benefits, and uses of the product, as well as display and promote the product brand (Kotler and Keller, 2016). In line with this opinion according to Kristiawan and Keni (2020) Packaging is not only viewed from its function as a wrapper or container for a product but more than that it can influence consumer perceptions of the product and have an impact on purchasing decisions. Consumers' assessment of product packaging can be viewed from the color, shape design, size, and materials used for packaging a product (Prasetya et al., 2018).

➤ *Motivation*

Motivation is the impetus felt by someone to obtain and fulfill desires and expectations (Dewi et al, 2017). Purchase motivation is driven by the discomfort felt by consumers so that a need is formed to overcome this discomfort by buying products or services (Wijaya, 2017). Consumer's purchase motivation consists of two dimensions, namely utilitarian shopping motives and hedonic shopping motives. Utilitarian motivation is a rational motivation because purchases are driven by the need to obtain functional benefits from the product or service. On the other hand, hedonic motivation is a psychological and emotional motivation that arises because of the urge to meet social demands and subjective feelings such as prestige, personal satisfaction, and emotional satisfaction (Priansa, 2017). Purchase motivation as an incentive to make purchases is certainly a determining factor in purchasing decisions, the higher the consumer's motivation

to meet their needs, the stronger the urge to make purchasing decisions (Dewi, Siburian, Indriastuti, 2017).

➤ *Price*

Price is defined as compensation in the form of money given to consumers as an exchange rate for the use and utilization of a product or service by consumers (Ningrum and Maddinsyah, 2021). In setting the price there are indicators that must be considered, including price affordability, which means the price set by the producer must be affordable by the intended consumer, and adjusting the price with quality and benefits and adjusting the price with the purchasing power of the intended consumer. Price is one of the important factors considered by consumers and determines purchase decisions (Alfairi, 2019).

➤ *Brand Image*

Brand image is consumer perception and understanding of the uniqueness and characteristics of a product or a company that produces the product (Girsang at al, 2020). Furthermore, according to Widyaningrum and Mani (2021) brand image represents consumer perceptions of brands that are created from information and consumer experiences in using products from certain brands. With regard to multivitamin consumption, Rini et al (2021) found that consumer buying interest in multivitamin C products is influenced by brand image, which means that the better brand image of a vitamin C product, so the consumer's interest in buying and consuming multivitamin C from a particular brand will be greater.

➤ *Thinking Framework*

The thinking framework is design based on the theory and previous study and it could be described as follows:

Fig 1 Thinking Framework
Source: Theoretical Review

➤ *Hypothesis*

- H1: Halal products influence the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta.
- H2: Packaging influence the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta.
- H3: Motivation influence the purchase decision of multivitamins Redoxon in DKI Jakarta.
- H4: Price influences influence the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta.
- H5: Brand image influence the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta.
- H6: Purchase decision influence the repurchase of Redoxon multivitamins in Jakarta.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted to examine the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable presented in the form of a research hypothesis, therefore associative quantitative research was used with the explanatory survey method. The variables in this study include Halal Products (X₁), Packaging (X₂), Motivation (X₃), Price (X₄), and Brand Image (X₅) and the dependent variable in study are the purchase decision (Y₁) and Repurchase (Y₂) multivitamin Redoxon. The population in this study were consumers of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta, and the samples were taken using a purposive sampling technique. In this study, the total users of redoxone vitamin products were not clearly known, so the formula N = (total number of indicators x 5) was used to sample the sample. So that the total number of samples in this study is = 24 x 5 = 120 respondents. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to predetermined samples. Furthermore, the data were analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis technique through the SmartPLS program.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Measurement Evaluation Model (Outer Model)*

Fig 2 Outer Model Analysis
Source: Data Processing Result (2023)

- Based on the processed data, we find that all indicators have an outer loading value above 0.5. This value according to Ghazali (2015) is considered sufficient to meet the requirements and appropriate to use.

➤ *The Average Variance Extract (AVE)*

Table 1 The Average Variance Extract (AVE) Results

Variable	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Buying decision	0.560
Repeat purchase	0.716
Halal products	0.724
Packaging	0.729
Brand Image	0.619
Price	0.761
Motivation	0.726

Source: Data Processing Result (2023)

- The average variance extract (AVE) value for all variables obtained a value above 0.5, so that it was considered eligible.

➤ *Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larckel)*

Table 2 Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test Results

	Brand Image	Price	Buying decision	Motivation	Packaging	Repeat purchase	Halal products
Brand Image	0.787						
Price	0.798	0.872					
Buying decision	0.754	0.721	0.749				
Motivation	0.865	0.804	0.811	0.852			
Packaging	0.800	0.748	0.778	0.853	0.854		
Repeat purchase	0.771	0.732	0.799	0.784	0.766	0.846	
Halal products	0.799	0.718	0.750	0.822	0.823	0.770	0.851

Source: Data Processing Result (2023)

- From the data in the table above, all variables have an AVE root value greater than the correlation value between one construct and another, so discriminant validity is considered appropriate.

➤ Composite Reliability

Table 3 Composite Reliability Test Result

Variable	Composite reliability	Alpha Cronbach
Buying decision	0.924	0.920
Repeat purchase	0.939	0.933
Halal products	0.929	0.923
Packaging	0.939	0.937
Brand Image	0.927	0.922
Price	0.904	0.895
Motivation	0.937	0.922

Source: Data Processing Result (2023)

- Based on the data shown in Table 4, each variable has a composite reliability value above 0.7, so it is considered have high or good reliability.

➤ R-Square (R²)

Based on the data processing that has been carried out using the smartPLS program, the R-Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4 R- square (R²) Test Result

	R-Square
Buying Decision	0.699
Repeat Purchase	0.638

Source: Data Processing Result (2023)

Based on the data presented in table 4.16 above, it is known that the R-Square value for the purchase decision variable is 0.699. The acquisition of this value explains that the influence of halal products, packaging, motivation, price and brand image on the purchase decision is 0.699 or 69%. Then the R-Square value obtained by the repurchase variable is 0.638. This value explains that repurchasing is influenced by purchasing decisions by 63%.

➤ Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis test in this study is conducted based on the path coefficient which contains the original sample value, the T-statistics value and the P-value which determines the direction of the relationship between variables and the level of significance of the relationship. Furthermore, the results of the Smart PLS program are shown in the following table.

Table 5 Hypothesis Test Result

	Original sample	Sample average	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P value
Halal Products -> Purchase Decision	0.142	0.141	0.067	2.127	0.033
Packaging -> Purchase Decision	0.211	0.211	0.067	3.172	0.002
Motivation -> Purchase Decision	0.370	0.368	0.101	3,644	0.000
Price -> Purchase Decision	0.117	0.118	0.062	1886	0.059
Brand Image -> Purchase Decision	0.058	0.061	0.086	0.678	0.498
Purchase Decision -> Repurchase	0.799	0.800	0.030	26,657	0.000

Source: Data Processing Result (2023)

- Based on the data in the tabel above, it can be explained as follows:
 - ✓ The original value of the variable sample of halal products on purchase decisions is 0.142 and that value positive value, then halal products have a positive effect on purchase decisions. Furthermore, the T-statistic value of the halal product variable on the purchasing decision variable is 2.127>T table 1.966 and the P-Value is 0.033>0.05. Based on the result it can be concluded that halal products have a significant effect on the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamin in DKI Jakarta, then the hypothesis is accepted.
 - ✓ The value of the original sample packaging variable on purchasing decisions of 0.211 and the value is close to +1, so that packaging has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Furthermore, the T-statistic value of the packaging variable on the purchasing decision variable is 3.172 > T table 1.966 and the P-Value is 0.002 <0.05. From these results it can be concluded that packaging influences the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta, and the hypothesis is accepted.

- ✓ The original sample value of the motivation variable on purchasing decisions which is 0.370 and the value is close to +1, so that motivation has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Furthermore, the T-statistic value of the motivational variable on the purchased decision variable is $3.644 > T$ table 1.966 and the P-Value is $0.000 < 0.05$. From these results it can be concluded that motivation influences the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta, so the hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ The original sample price variable on purchasing decisions is 0.117 and the value is close to +1, so that the price has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. However, the T-statistic value of the price variable on the purchasing decision variable is $1.886 < T$ table 1.966 and the P-Value is $1.886 > 0.05$. From these results it can be concluded that price has no effect on the purchase decision Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta, so the hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ The original sample value of the brand image variable on purchasing decisions is 0.058 and that value close to +1, so that is brand image has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. However, the calculated T-statistic value of the Brand Image variable on the purchasing decision variable is $0.678 < T$ table 1.966 and the P-Value is $0.498 > 0.05$. From these results it can be concluded that brand image has no effect on the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamin in DKI Jakarta, so the hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ The original sample value of the purchase decision variable on repurchase is 0.799 and the value is close to +1, so that that repurchasing has a positive effect on repurchasing. Furthermore, the T-statistic value of the purchase decision variable on the repurchase variable is $26.657 > T$ table 1.966 and the P-Value is $0.000 < 0.05$. From these results it can be concluded that purchasing decisions affect the repurchasing of Redoxon multivitamins in Jakarta, so the hypothesis is accepted.

V. DISCUSSION

First hypothesis (H1) was accepted. It was proved that halal products have a significant effect on the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamin in DKI Jakarta. This finding supports the results of research by Tri Nur Fadilah, Purwanto and Achmad Nur Alfianto (2020) and research by Ichsani Mutiara and Syahputra (2018) which also proves that halal products have a positive and significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions. Based on the research results, it can be interpreted that halal products have a very important role for consumers in determining the decision to buy a product. Product halalness is the main consideration for consumers when choosing a product, therefore a product must be able to convince consumers that it is halal. When consumers believe a product is a halal product from its contents, the manufacturing process which is validated by the existence of a halal product label, the tendency of consumers to decide to buy the product will be higher than products whose halal status is not believed.

The second hypothesis (H2) is accepted, it can be concluded that packaging influences the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta. This result is in line with the research by Iranita (2020) and Ovalina Sylvia Br. Ginting1, Ahmad Arif Affandi (2022) who also found that packaging had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Packaging or packages for Redoxon multivitamins that are round, with attractive colors, as well as the brand name that is clearly displayed on the packaging play a very important role in attracting consumers to make purchases.

The third hypothesis (H3) is accepted, it can be concluded that motivation influences the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta. The results of this study are supported by research by Dewi Urip Wahyuni (2008) and Yanda Satriaso (2011) who also found that motivation influences purchasing decisions. This research was conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic, there was an urgency for the community to maintain their health in order to minimize the risk of infected by Covid-19 virus so that the community's need for multivitamins was very high. The strong motivation of consumers to consume multivitamins makes the tendency of consumers to buy Redoxon multivitamins to be very high.

The fourth hypothesis (H4) was rejected, price has no effect on the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta. The results of this study are different from the research of Adi Nurmahdi, Christianto Hadisiswanto Putro (2020) and Adi Nurmahdi, Christianto Muhammad Thariq Nahra Putra (2020) who found that price influences purchasing decisions. In this study it was found that price had no effect on the decision to consume Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta. The price has no effect on the decision to consume Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta, it can be related to the period of this research which was carried out during the Covid-19 pandemic, there is a very strong urgency for the public to consume quality multivitamins to maintain endurance and stamina to avoid the Covid-19 virus. These conditions make price no longer a consideration for people to buy multivitamins. People are willing to spend their money to buy multivitamins even though they are expensive in order to maintain their health.

The fifth hypothesis (H5) was rejected, brand image has no effect on the decision to consume Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta. The results of this study differ from the findings of Adi Nurmahdi, Prapatantio Teteg Pringgogidgoyo (2022), Adi Nurmahdi, Roy Harry Martin Siregar (2021) and Suhesti Ningsih, Sri Laksmi Pradanawati, 2021 who found that brand image influences purchasing decisions. On the other hand, this research is in line with the research of Tria Putri, Marwan Marwan and Rose Rahmidani (2018) and Sumiati, Deni Gea (2021) which also found that brand image has no effect on purchasing decisions. The absence of a significant effect of brand image on purchasing decisions can be caused by the timing of this research which was carried out during the Covid-19 period. Brand image is no longer an urgency for the public in making decisions to purchase multivitamins, because the priority for the community is quality multivitamins that can maintain their stamina and

endurance to minimize the risk of exposure to the Covid-19 virus.

The sixth hypothesis (H6) was accepted, it can be concluded that purchasing decisions affect the repurchasing of Redoxon multivitamins in Jakarta, so the hypothesis is accepted. The results of this study are in line with the results of Ali 's research (2019) which found that there is a positive influence between purchasing decisions on repurchasing . That is, the more satisfied consumers are with their purchase decisions, the higher the tendency to repurchase. Redoxon Multivitamin consumers have a good assessment of the benefits after consuming it, so there is a very high tendency for consumers to buy Redoxon multivitamin again.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that halal products, packaging, and motivation have a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta. However, price and brand image have no significant effect on the purchase decision of Redoxon multivitamins in DKI Jakarta. Furthermore, purchase decision has significant effect on repurchasing of Redoxon multivitamin in DKI Jakarta. Based on the R-Square value, the influence of halal products, packaging, motivation, price and brand image on purchasing decisions is 0.699 or 69%, further researchers are advised to review and compare the effects of halal products, packaging, motivation, price and brand image on repurchase decisions and repurchase decisions with a wider scope of research and a larger number of samples, not only in DKI Jakarta but nationally.

The company are advised to increase consumer motivation to consume Multivitamin Redoxon. The efforts that can be made include more aggressively educating and socializing the community regarding the benefits of Redoxon multivitamins which contain complete vitamins to maintain a healthy body and minimize the risk of exposure to harmful viruses. Furthermore, the company is advised to increase public perception of the halalness of Multivitamin Redoxon products. Companies need to increase socialization and campaigns to provide information to consumers that Redoxon is a halal product for consumption and already has a halal label from the MUI, campaigning that Redoxon multivitamin is a supplement that can meet the body's vitamin needs and is beneficial for increasing immunity and increasing consumer perceptions of Redoxon Multivitamin product safety to consume. The company is also advised to maintain the clarity of the brand name on the Multivitamin Redoxon packaging, maintain the shape of the packaging, and further improve packaging materials that are more environmentally friendly.

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